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Research Article

STUDY OF THE CONSEQUENCES AND COMPLICATIONS OF THE EARLY VERSUS DELAYED LUMBER DISC SURGERY AMONG 314 PATIENTS IN MULTAN

¹Dr Alia Khanum, ²Dr Bismillah Noor, ³Dr Sania Nasrullah
^{1,2,3}Nishter Hospital Multan.

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Abstract:

Aim and Methods: In a retrospective study the clinical presentations, neurological findings, contrast studies, operative findings, and the follow-up results of 314 patients with disc herniation were studied over a two years duration. This disease was most frequent between the ages of 30 to 40 and mostly in males. Low back pain with or without radicular pain was the most frequent symptom, involving the left leg in the majority of patients and the average duration of pain was more than a year.

Place and Duration: In the Neurosurgery department of Nishter Hospital Multan for two years duration from March 2018 to March 2020.

Results: In this study L4 -L5 disc herniation had the highest frequency (50%). The most encouraging sign to perform myelography was motor deficit (57%). Postoperatively, our patients were followed for an average of 12 months with excellent to good results noted in 96% of them. Reherniation of a previously resected disc was noted only in two patients (0.6%).

Conclusion: It is concluded that with precise selection we could have more than 90% good results in a conventional method of disc surgery and the chances of recurrence are negligible.

Keywords: Disc, low back pain, discectomy, sciatica.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Alia Khanum,
Nishter Hospital Multan.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Low back pain is probably the most frequent cause of human suffering after headache. Almost 80% of human beings will experience low back pain at one time during their life. Low back pain may be the result of the erect position of man since it is less frequent in animals, which use their front and hind legs to support their body. The erect position in man results in displacement of the center of-gravity of the human body. The tremendous weight of the upper extremities, trunk, and head is placed upon the intervertebral discs, as shock absorbers, making them vulnerable to disc rupture and herniation. The first record of signs and symptoms of ruptured intervertebral disc in the form of radicular pain was recorded by Soranus. Walter Dandy was the first to operate on patients with bilateral sciatica. He noticed pieces of cartilage inside canal and called them enchondroma. The correlation of sciatic pain to disc herniation was definitely proved by Mixter and Barr in 1934. Since the introduction of myelography, CT scan, and MRI the diagnosis and treatment of disc herniation has become much easier. In this article we discuss the clinical presentations and surgical results of 314 cases of disc herniation with a specific reference to late results and the chances of reherniation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This retrospective study was held in the Neurosurgery department of Nishtar Hospital Multan for two years duration from March 2018 to March 2020. Almost 22.5% of all patients had low back pain with or without sciatica. With conservative treatment over a 4-6-week period only a minority of these patients, meaning 314 patients (5.6%), required disc surgery. 206 were male and 108 were female (male to female ratio 2:1). 58% of the patients were 30 to 49 years old (range 16 to 73 years) (Table I). More than 50% had symptoms of more than one-year duration (Table II). Almost 98% of the patients had radicular pain, with or

without back pain. The left leg was most frequently involved (44.5%, Table III). Positive SLR (straight leg raising test) was noticed in 233 (74%), sensory deficit in 192 (61%), and motor deficit in 175 patients (67%). Abnormal deep tendon reflexes (DTR) was noticed in 151 (48%), and evidence of sphincter dysfunction in only seven patients (2%). The plain x-ray was abnormal in 35.3% and the most frequent abnormality was spondylosis (55 patients, 16.8%). In the remaining patients we could notice a variety of abnormalities (Table IV). In 157 (50%) of the patients the L4-L5 disc herniation was found on myelography and only a single level was involved in 256 patients. In 53 patients (17%) the operation was performed at two, and in five patients (1.5%) at three levels (Table V).

Surgical Exploration:

Surgical exploration was judged as the best method to relieve the dual and radicular compression. In 100 patients (31.8%) only fenestration was performed, while laminectomy and hemilaminectomy was done in 54.2% of patients. Interlaminar approach and the Cloward technique of fenestration were used in only 13%.

RESULTS:

The most frequent complication after surgery was superficial soft tissue infection which was noted in 12 patients (3.8%). Discitis, vascular injury, CSF leakage, and bilateral root drop were each noted in one patient, and unilateral foot drop was present in two patients. Therefore, the total percentage of complications was 5.7%.

All the patients were followed for at least one year and the results of the operation were as follows: complete disappearance or pain in 264 (84%), good result in 38 (12%), and fair and poor result in 12 (4%). During the follow up, two patients had reherniation which was again managed surgically.

Table I. Age distribution in 314 cases of disc herniation who were explored

Age	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	70-79
No.	3(0.9)	58(18)	96(30)	90(28)	55(17)	9(2)	3(0.9)

Table II. Duration of symptoms in 314 patients with herniation who were operated

Symptom Duration	Number	Percent
Less than one month	16	3.5%
1-3 Month	29	6.3%
3-6 Month	31	6.7%
6-12 Month	71	15.4%
Less than one year	147	31.9%
More than one year	165	35.8%
underdetermined	2	0.4%
Total	461	100.0%

Table III. Distribution of pain in 314 patients with disc herniation who underwent exploration

Pain distribution	Number	Percent
L.B.P. with radiation to left leg	140	44.6%
L.B.P. with radiation to right leg	112	35.7%
L.B.P. with radiation to both leg	39	12.4%
left sided sciatica only	12	3.8%
right sided sciatica only	3	1.0%
bilateral sciatica only	1	0.3%
L.B.P. only	5	1.6%
without any pain	2	0.6%
Total	314	100.0%

Table IV. Plain radiography in 314 patients with disc surgery who came to exploration

X-ray findings	Number	Percent
spondylosis	55	12.8%
sacralization	20	4.6%
lumbarization	2	0.5%
L4-L5 collapse	8	1.9%
L5-S1 collapse	20	4.6%
lysis and olisthesis	6	1.4%
scoliosis	6	1.4%
abnormal x-ray	111	25.8%
normal x-ray	203	47.1%

Table V. Disc herniation in 314 patients according- to lite pathologic level

Level	Number	Percent
L1-L2	2	0.6%
L2-L3	8	2.5%
L3-L4	18	5.7%
L4-L5	157	50.0%
L5-S1	75	23.8%
L1-L2 and L2-L3	1	0.3%
L2-L3 and L3-L4	2	0.6%
L3-L4 and L4-L5	16	5.0%
L4-L5 and L5-S1	31	9.8%
L3-L4, L4-L5 and L5-S1	3	0.9%

DISCUSSION:

Almost 20% of the patients seen in our clinic suffered from low back pain with or without sciatica, and among these only 5% ended up having surgical exploration. The surgical and conservative treatment of disc herniation or sciatica remains an enigma. This is probably due to the fact that low back pain can result from irritation or destruction of the various pain-producing structures of the back and the trunk, meaning the musculoskeletal, vascular, and soft tissue structures or the lower back region. Over the years since the surgical exploration of Mixler and Barr, there has been a tendency for less aggressive treatment of disc herniation. The old laminectomies were replaced by laminotomies, fenestrations, and microsurgical exploration of the disc space. Recently, more conservative approach have been applied using the percutaneous nucleotome. We tried to be as conservative as possible; i.e. the patient with low back and radicular pain was treated with medication and rest for at least four to six weeks before a decision was made for surgical exploration. Undoubtedly, clinical course and the presence or neurological deficit were taken into consideration. When surgical treatment was decided, we considered the psychologic situation, clinical presentation, physical exam, and myelography findings. It was not surprising that almost an overwhelming majority of patients had radicular pain. L4-L5 disc herniation seems more frequent in this country. In some reports, such as that of Fennison, the incidence is more frequent in L5-S1 interspace. Morshed has studied more than 4000 patients and according to his experience also, the frequency of L4-L5 disc herniation is higher in Iran. The success rate of more than 95% is probably due to the diligent patient selection. The recurrence, which occurred in two patients, is compatible with that of the literature.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, if patients are selected carefully based on the clinical presentation, psychology, neurological exam, and myelographic findings, the success rate is more than 95% and also the recurrence rate of disc herniation is negligible.

REFERENCES:

1. Leer-Salvesen, Sunniva, Eva Dybvik, Anette H. Ranhoff, Bjørn Liljestrand Husebø, Ola E. Dahl, Lars B. Engesæter, and Jan-Erik Gjertsen. "Do direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) cause delayed surgery, longer length of hospital stay, and poorer outcome for hip fracture patients?." *European Geriatric Medicine* (2020).
2. Sakai, Yusuke, Takashi Kaito, Shota Takenaka, Tomoya Yamashita, Takahiro Makino, Naobumi Hosogane, Kenya Nojiri et al. "Complications after spinal fixation surgery for osteoporotic vertebral collapse with neurological deficits: Japan Association of Spine Surgeons with ambition multicenter study." *Journal of Orthopaedic Science* 24, no. 6 (2019): 985-990.
3. Reid, Daniel BC, Shyam A. Patel, Alan H. Daniels, and Jeffrey A. Rihn. "Vascular complications in spine surgery." In *Seminars in Spine Surgery*, vol. 31, no. 4, p. 100756. WB Saunders, 2019.
4. Khalifeh, Jawad M., Christopher F. Dibble, Ammar H. Hawasli, and Wilson Z. Ray. "Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System physical function and pain interference in spine surgery." *Journal of Neurosurgery: Spine* 31, no. 2 (2019): 165-174.
5. Fanous, Andrew A., John Paul G. Kolcun, G. Damian Brusko, Michael Paci, George M. Ghobrial, Jonathan Nakhla, Ananth Eleswarapu, Nathan H. Lebowhl, Barth A. Green, and Joseph P. Gjolaj. "Surgical Site Infection as a Risk Factor for Long-Term Instrumentation Failure in Patients with Spinal Deformity: A Retrospective Cohort Study." *World neurosurgery* 132 (2019): e514-e519.
6. Ghirelli, Michael, Giulia Molinari, Maria Rosini, Federico De Iure, Alessandro Gasbarrini, Francesco Mattioli, Matteo Alicandri-Ciufelli, and Livio Presutti. "Pharyngo-esophageal perforations after anterior cervical spine surgery: management and outcomes." *World Neurosurgery* (2020).
7. Tan, Terence, Hui Lee, Milly S. Huang, Joost Rutges, Travis E. Marion, Joseph Mathew, Mark Fitzgerald et al. "Prophylactic postoperative measures to minimize surgical site infections in spine surgery: systematic review and evidence summary." *The Spine Journal* 20, no. 3 (2020): 435-447.
8. Yan, Yingzhao, Congcong Wu, Congan Huang, Zengjie Zhang, Jianle Wang, Aimin Wu, and Xiangyang Wang. "The Presence of Thyroid Cartilage at the Surgical Level Reduces Early Dysphagia after Single-Level Anterior Cervical Surgery: A Retrospective Study." *Journal of Investigative Surgery* 33, no. 4 (2020): 365-374.
9. Takeuchi, Hirohito, Itaru Oda, Shigeki Oshima, Masaru Suzuki, and Masanori Fujiya. "Is the administration of vancomycin to operative field effective? Studying from operative wound drainage tube culture." *European Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery & Traumatology* 30, no. 2 (2020): 215-219.

10. Goel, Atul, Ravikiran Vutha, Abhidha Shah, Pralhad Dharurkar, Neha Jadhav, and Dikpal Jadhav. "Spinal kyphoscoliosis associated with Chiari formation and syringomyelia 'recovery' following atlantoaxial fixation: a preliminary report and early results based on experience with 11 surgically treated cases." *World neurosurgery* 125 (2019): e937-e946.
11. Goel, Nicholas J., Prateek Agarwal, Arka N. Mallela, Kalil G. Abdullah, Zarina S. Ali, Ali K. Ozturk, Neil R. Malhotra, James M. Schuster, and H. Isaac Chen. "Liver disease is an independent predictor of poor 30-day outcomes following surgery for degenerative disease of the cervical spine." *The Spine Journal* 19, no. 3 (2019): 448-460.
12. Ren, Jian, Tao Hong, Chuan He, Xiaoyu Li, Yongjie Ma, Jiaying Yu, Feng Ling, and Hongqi Zhang. "Surgical approaches and long-term outcomes of intramedullary spinal cord cavernous malformations: a single-center consecutive series of 219 patients." *Journal of Neurosurgery: Spine* 31, no. 1 (2019): 123-132.
13. Zhong, Yuxian, JinYu Liu, Weijin Zhou, and Ding Yu. "Relationship between straight leg-raising test measurements and area of fat infiltration in multifidus muscles in patients with lumbar disc herniation." *Journal of back and musculoskeletal rehabilitation* Preprint (2019): 1-7.
14. Rustagi, Tarush, Swamy Kurra, Katherine Sullivan, Ravi Dhawan, and William F. Lavelle. "Surgical treatment of early-onset idiopathic scoliosis in the United States: a trend analysis of 15 years (1997–2012)." *The Spine Journal* 19, no. 2 (2019): 314-320.
15. Shah, Neil V., Joshua D. Lavian, Cameron R. Moattari, Ishaan Jain, Saad Tarabichi, Peter G. Passias, Joseph Scollan et al. "P150. The impact of preoperative cannabis use on outcomes following thoracolumbar spinal fusion: a propensity score-matched analysis." *The Spine Journal* 19, no. 9 (2019): S227-S228.